

Tick reference card

Compare your tick against the ticks below
(approx. size)

A. variegatum
Tropical Bont tick

A. hebraeum
S. African Bont tick

M♂

F♀

Bont ticks
(*Amblyomma spp.*)

5 mm

Bont-legged ticks
(*Hyalomma spp.*)

Red-legged tick
(*Rhipicephalus evertsi evertsi*)

Approx. distribution

Found a tick?
Submit your record!

(Most common hard ticks collected in Botswana 2024–25)

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